

SCIENCE TEACHERS' COMPETENCE REFLECTIVE OF THE NEW NORMAL FLEXIBLE LEARNING MODALITIES

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Science Teachers' Competence Reflective of the New Normal Flexible Learning Modalities

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the Science Teachers' competence reflective of the new normal flexible learning modalities for the school year 2022-2023 at Carcar City Division as basis for a teacher support model. The study is quantitative in nature which utilized the descriptive-correlational design to determine the competencies of the Science teachers focused on the areas of Classroom Management, Instructional Delivery, Formative Assessment and Personal Competencies. Findings revealed that majority of the respondents were 31-40 years old, female, with MA units, General Science major, holders of Teacher 3 positions who had attended various training relevant to science. They had teaching experience of 1-5 and 6-10 years respectively. It was further shown that the Science teachers were Highly Competent based on their competencies as rated by the teachers, master teachers and principals. Furthermore, no direct correlation has been found on the demographic profile and their competency. Science teachers as educators should demonstrate the following competencies to promote purposeful learning among the students.

Keywords: *science teachers, teaching competencies, descriptive-correlational*

Introduction

Science is the systematic study of the structure and behavior of the physical, social, and natural worlds through observation and experimentation. It is also the integral part when teaching science. One of the goals of science teaching across the world is to provide every learner quality education to become scientifically competent for global advancement in science education. Azuelo et al. (2014) mentioned that in the educational paradigm shifts, there have been many changes in the school system across the globe which include teaching approaches, curriculum framework, learning styles of the students, and academic related policies.

On the other hand, educational communities across the world proposed educational reform agenda in teaching competencies in science to meet the demands in preparing future citizens for scientific literacy in the 21st century. As mentioned in Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (2015), the educational goals in the entire world transcend knowledge acquisition by including competencies that encompasses four areas namely: classroom management, instructional delivery, formative assessment, and personal competency to live in the current global educational society.

Furthermore, teachers should be innovative in strengthening their competencies as they continue to cater to the needs of the learners in the teaching and learning process anchored on the learner-centered pedagogical approach (Barrot, 2015). Thus, the primordial role of the teachers is to guide the learners through giving feedback and assessment to help student keep on track. In the time of educational paradigm shifts, there have been many changes in the school system which include teaching performance and pedagogy, curriculum formats, learning styles, and the related academic policies. The researcher has been teaching science for almost 10 years and has observed problems in the performance of the students in science. In fact, in the last 3-year results of Division Assessment Test, it revealed that there was only an average of 45%-50% MPS in science which was lower compared to other subjects (DAT, 2019).

As the result, the teachers must strengthen their teaching pedagogy to help improve students' needs. Thus, the school helps in cultivating capabilities such as exercising self-directed learning of the students in science and across all learning areas. These goals are addressed to intensify the teachers' teaching competencies in the delivery of learning instructions. It is expected that science teachers will develop students' proficiency in science which creates opportunities to students pursue progressively higher levels of study, prepares them for science-related occupations, and engages them in science-related activities appropriate to their interests and abilities. Therefore, the researcher assessed the teachers' teaching competencies and performances in science reflective to the new normal flexible learning modalities and used the result of this study as the basis for crafting a teacher support model.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: their age, sex, educational attainment, area of specialization, teaching position, trainings attended relevant to science teaching and how many training attended per level, years of teaching experience in science, grades of the students, and teachers' competence on their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form?
2. What is the extent of the teachers' teaching competencies in the teaching of science in terms of classroom management, instructional delivery, formative assessment, and personal competencies?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the teachers' competencies in teaching of science in terms of their classroom management, instructional delivery, formative assessment, and personal competencies?
4. Based on the results of the study, what model can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive -correlational methods of research. It is descriptive in nature because it described the profile of the Science teacher in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, area of specialization, teaching position, training attended relevant to science teaching and number of training attended per level, years of teaching experience in science, and the teachers' competence reflected on their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. The study also gathered the academic grades of the students related to the teaching competencies of the science teachers as stipulated in the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. The study further utilized the correlational method because the variables involved were correlated.

Respondents

The study was conducted in Carcar City, a 5th class component city in the province of Cebu. There were eleven (11) Public Secondary High Schools under Carcar City Division. These schools were Roberto E. Sato Memorial National High School, Valencia Vocational National High School, Tal-ut National High School, Carcar Central National High School, Hunob National High School, Puesto Integrated High School, Ocana National High School, Maximino Memorial National High School, Gelacio C. Babao Memorial National High School, Perrelos National High School, and Tuyom National High School. The respondents of this study were the 11 Secondary High Schools science teachers who were eligible teachers handling Science subject in their respective schools. They were selected by the researcher using a purposive sampling technique. In teachers' perceptions, the top 10 students were used to validate the quantitative data, but not made to answer the quantitative questions. On the qualitative phase of this study, the selected ten (10) key informants composed of science honor students.

Instrument

This study utilized a researcher- made questionnaire focusing on the science teachers' competence reflective of the normal flexible learning modalities. The questionnaire utilized in this study was based on the Science curriculum guide and IPCRF's priority indicators for proficient teachers. The questionnaire is divided into two (2) parts; part 1 contained the data on demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the respondents' age, sex, educational attainment, area of specialization, teaching position and training attended relevant to science teaching and how many training attended per level number of teaching experience and part 2 contained the statements on teachers' competencies in the teaching of science in terms of classroom management, instructional delivery, formative assessment and personal competencies. Hence, this discussion is dealt with utmost confidentiality.

Procedure

This study used specific steps to collect data. First, the researcher asked permission to the Dean of the Graduate Studies of Negros Oriental State University addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent of Carcar City Division to guarantee the support of the school heads in each school. Second, as soon as the researcher was granted permission, he then started conducted the study on the date scheduled. The survey questionnaire was personally distributed to the teacher respondents of the study. Other respondents answered via Online Google form since they preferred to answer in Google form. Third, the researcher retrieved the accomplished tool immediately after the respondents answer completely the questionnaires.

Ethical Considerations

This research followed ethical guidelines and ethics. Research ethics matter for scientific integrity, human rights and dignity, and collaboration between science and society. These principles make sure that participation in studies is voluntary, informed, and safe for research subjects. During the conduct of the study, the participants are free to opt in or out of the study at any point in time. Participants know the purpose, benefits, risks, and funding behind the study before they agree or decline to join. Confidentiality of the participants in which information are hidden and used pseudonyms. Physical, social, psychological and all other types of harm are kept to an absolute minimum. This study ensured that the work is free of plagiarism or research misconduct, and accurately presented the results.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Male	13	23.64
Female	42	76.36
Total	55	100.00

The results revealed (see Table 1) that there were 42 out of 55 or 76.36% female respondents while 13 out of 55 or 23.64% were males. This implies that majority of the respondents were female science teachers. It is important to determine the sex profile of the science teachers as to look significant evidence to demonstrate that biological and social differences between women, men, girls, boys, and gender-diverse people contribute to differences in their teaching competencies. This implies that gender distribution is common among

most school of other division where female becomes more in population than male (Skelton, 2012).

Table 2. Educational Attainment Profile of the Respondents

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
BS Degree	15	27.27
MA Academic Requirement	25	45.45
MA Degree	5	9.09
Doctorate Academic Requirement	10	18.18
Total	55	100.00

The results showed (see Table 2) that 25 out of 55 or 45.45% were MA Academic Requirement, 15 out of 55 or 27.27% were BS Degree holder, 10 out of 55 or 18.18% were having their Doctorate Academic Requirement and 5 out of 55 or 9.09% were MA Degree. This implies that majority of the science teachers had Master of Art completed the academic requirement. Earning a master's degree has advantages that many science teachers must look forward to. A Science teacher with a master's degree in science has provided greater opportunity since one of the requirements that a science teacher must be promoted is through earning higher professional degree. Through continuing education, it allows teachers to develop their specialized expertise in their area of interest. This will also help improve their teaching pedagogy and practice (Hammond & Snowden (2016).

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents

<i>Area of Specialization</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
General Science	25	45.45
Biology	19	34.55
Chemistry/Physics	10	18.18
Others	1	1.82
Total	55	100.00

As shown in Table 3, there were 25 out of 55 or 45.45% of the respondents took General Science major, 19 out of 55 or 19% of the respondents were Biology major, 10 out of 55 or 18.8% were Chemistry/Physics majors and only 1 was other major. This further revealed that majority of the respondents were General Science major. It implies that among the groups of respondents, the general science teachers appear to be the most efficient. Considering this, it is deemed necessary to identify the areas of expertise and instructional effectiveness of public secondary school science teachers in terms of their understanding of the science curriculum. According to Edson, Manalansan, & Fogatal (2017) that a personal preference is one more justification for teachers to focus on general science as their chosen field of specialization.

Table 4. Teaching Position Profile of the Respondents

<i>Teaching Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Teacher 1	10	18.18
Teacher 2	12	21.82
Teacher 3	23	41.82
MT 1	9	16.36
MT 2	1	1.82
Total	55	100.00

As glimpsed (see Table 4), 23 out of 55 or 41.82% were Teacher 3, 12 out of 55 or 21.82% were Teacher 2, 10 out of 55 or 18.18% were Teacher 1, 9 out of 55 or 16.36% were Master Teacher 1 and only 1 out of 55 or 1.82% was Master Teacher 2. This implies that majority of the science teacher respondents were Teacher 3. To be eligible for teacher 3 position, the science teachers should have at least a Very Satisfactory Performance Rating for the last three (3) rating periods prior to his/her application for promotion as teacher 3. This implies that the promotion of teachers to higher ranks is contingent upon their meeting the standards set forth in the Department of Education's mission, as stated in the guidelines of Executive Order No. 0174, which established the Expanded Career Progression System for Public School Teachers.

According to Bongco (2019) the Department of Education have issued policies and guidelines that would ensure equal chances of every member of the profession to the said opportunities. The teachers have the chances to be promoted from Teacher 1 to Teacher 3 and Master 1 to Master 3 if they complied and meet the set requirements for promotions.

Table 5. Number of Hours of Training Attended Relevant to Science Teaching of the Respondents

<i>Number of Hours</i>	<i>International Level</i>		<i>National Level</i>		<i>Regional Level</i>		<i>Division Level</i>	
	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
1 – 10	42	76.36	5	9.09	2	3.64	7	12.73
11 – 20	5	9.09	22	40.00	0	0	2	3.64
21 – 30	7	12.73	11	20.00	4	7.27	3	5.45
31 – 40	0	0	9	16.36	27	49.09	18	32.71
≥ 41	1	1.82	8	14.55	22	40.00	25	45.45
Total	55	100.00	55	100.00	55	100.00	55	100.00

The results showed (see Table 5) that, in an international training, there were 42 out of 55 or 76.36% had attended 1 -10 hours, 7 out of 55 or 12.73% attended 21-30 hours, 5 out of 55 or 9.09 attended within 11- 20 hours and only 1 attended in 41 hours an above. For the national training, it was found out that 22 out of 55 or 40% attended within 11 -20 hours, 11 out of 55 or 20% had attended within 21-30 hours, 9 out of 55 or 16.36% attended the training in 31-40 hours, 8 out of 55 or 14.55% attended in more than 41 hours and 6 out of 55 or 9.09% had attended within 1-10 hours. For the Regional training, there were 27 out of 55 or 49.09 had attended within 31-40 hours, there were 22 out of 55 or 40% attended more than 41 hours, 4 out of 55 or 7.27% were attended within 21-30 hours and 2 out of 55 or 3.64% were attended within 1 -10 hours. For the Division training, there were 25 out of 55 or 45.45% attended 41 hours and above, 18 out of 55 or 32.71 were attended within 31-40 hours, 7 out of 55 or 12.73% were attended in 1 -10 hours, 3 out of 55 or 5.45% were attended within 21-30 hours and 2 out of 55 or 3.64 were attended within 11-20 hours. This implies that teachers in the Department of Education should be necessary to attend training and seminars. Inspiring them to become better teachers in the modern world, seminars will help create an effective learning environment, enhance teaching-learning scenarios, and keep them up to date on contemporary instructional devices. Teacher training is important for both experienced and those teachers who are new to the teaching profession to achieve the goal of the Department of Education on quality teaching and learning (Morgan, 2022).

Table 6. *Years of Teaching Experience in Science of the Respondents*

<i>Years of Teaching</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
1 – 5	20	36.36
6 – 10	20	36.36
11 – 15	11	20.00
≥ 16	4	7.28
Total	55	100.00

As reflected in the Table 6, it was found out that there were 20 out of 55 or 36.36% had teaching experience 1-5 years and 6-10 years respectively, there were 11 out of 55 or 20% had teaching experiences between 11-15 years and there were 4 out of 55 or 7.28% had teaching experiences of more 16 years. This implies that majority of the respondents had teaching experiences 1-5 years and 6-10 years respectively. Teaching experience matters but is not always a predictor of better performance of the teachers. However, the impact of experience is strongest during the first few years of teaching but does make assurance to be a predictor of their teaching competencies. As shown in table 6, less experienced teachers do not tend to be less effective than more experienced teachers. It was also found that teachers with the less experience (1-5 and 6-10) were found to be consulted and supported by professionals more regularly compared to teachers who had relatively more experience (11-15) and above. Therefore, it appears that less experienced teachers were found to be given more attention compared to relatively more experienced teachers considering that teachers with more teaching experience may not need training or support to teach in inclusive class, but the reality was not. Harris and Tim (2017) support that throughout a teacher's career, teaching experience is positively correlated with increases in student achievement.

Table 7. *Grades of the Students of the Respondents*

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
90% - 100%	Outstanding	53	96.36
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory	1	1.82
80% - 84%	Satisfactory	1	1.82
Total		55	100.00
Mean = 92.05	(Outstanding)		
sd = 2.26			

As shown in the Table 7, there were 53 out of 55 or 96.36% belongs to Outstanding Level and there was only 1 out of 55 or 1.82% belong to Very Satisfactory and Satisfactory respectively. This implies that majority of the students were outstanding learners in science. These students had made their academics a priority and more become independent and have desire for knowledge and understanding of the subject science. Outstanding students are those who performed remarkably and excel in the class in all learning areas. This implies that the teacher quality performance is a powerful predictor of student performance and has direct influence on students learning.

The teacher quality is the key central in student performance. It will transpire to the students' outcomes. In recent years, as study by Ortiz (2016) that there has been a significant rise in the study of teacher effectiveness where it has revealed that student achievement is strongly predicted by teachers' effectiveness.

Table 8. *Teachers' Competence based on Their IPCRF*

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	19	34.55
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	36	65.45
Total		55	100.00
Mean = 4.40	(Very Satisfactory)		
sd = 0.28			

As viewed in the Table 8, there were 36 out of 55 of 65.45% who belongs to very satisfactory level and 19 out of 55 or 34.55% of the science teachers were outstanding teachers. This denotes that majority of the teacher respondents were Very Satisfactory. This means that science teachers have displayed a high level of performance related skills and knowledge. The performance of the science teachers exceeded expectation and the goals and targets were achieved above the established standards. IPCRF helps teachers focus on student outcomes and plans activities for in-service education. It also encourages and recognizes excellence in teaching and to help teachers do their best to meet the Very Satisfactory rating. It is stipulated in the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form IPCRF which is an assessment tool for government employees such as teachers to rate the work done by the teacher over a period of one year.

Table 9. Teachers' Competencies in the Teaching of Science in Terms Classroom Management

The Science teacher...	Teachers		Principals		Master Teachers	
	\bar{wX}	VD	\bar{wX}	VD	\bar{wX}	VD
1. leads the class before the students either online classes or in actual classes.	3.24	C	3.25	HC	3.22	C
2. engages the student's participation inside the class or even on-line class.	3.29	HC	3.16	C	3.25	HC
3. treats the students with equal opportunity to other teachers' despites of the limited contact with the students.	3.45	HC	3.11	C	3.44	HC
4. builds a gap between teachers and students either online classes or in face-to-face classes.	3.40	HC	3.16	C	3.36	HC
5. is authoritarian in the conduct of classes or has complete control over their classroom.	3.33	HC	3.49	HC	3.35	HC
6. as a teaching style that tends to have a high level of involvement with their students.	3.40	HC	2.96	C	3.44	HC
7. is firm yet fair with the students.	3.36	HC	3.38	HC	3.33	HC
Composite	3.35	HC	3.22	C	3.34	HC

Legend: 1.00 – 1.74, Not Competent (NC); 1.75 – 2.49, Less Competent (LC); 2.50 – 3.24, Competent (C); 3.25 – 4.00, Highly Competent (HC)

As shown in the Table 9 on teachers' competencies in the teaching of science in terms classroom management and it was found out that the composite weighted mean of the teachers was 3.35 which interpreted as Highly Competent, while the composite mean of the school principals was 3.22 which interpreted as Competent, and the composite mean of the master teachers was 3.34 and interpreted as Highly Competent. This implies that the science teachers had establish and sustain an environment that fosters students' academic achievement in school despite that the school principals did not able to notice it. The school principals did not have full observation with the teachers on how the teachers performed their task in the delivery of learning applying the competencies. According to Stewart (2013) that the role of principal is helping teacher's professional development by sharing their expertise and experiences. There must be prompt feedback with the teachers to reevaluate their teaching methods in connections with the classroom management. This was supported by Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock (2019) cited that the principal's focus should be to develop and maintain effective educational programs within his/her school and to promote the improvement of teaching and learning.

Table 10. Teachers' Competencies in the Teaching of Science in Terms Instructional Delivery

The Science teacher...	Teachers		Principals		Master Teachers	
	\bar{wX}	VD	\bar{wX}	VD	\bar{wX}	VD
1. is able to deliver the lessons either face-to-face, online class or in modular learning modality.	3.36	HC	3.36	HC	3.25	HC
2. is flexible in the delivery of the lesson that he/she uses multiple modalities in transferring knowledge and skills to the students.	3.40	HC	3.22	C	3.42	HC
3. uses recorded video lesson as a supplemental on the topics that she/he had discussed.	3.18	C	3.11	C	3.18	C
4. uses a physical presence such as making eye to eye contact with the students.	3.44	HC	3.45	HC	3.22	C
5. conducts home visitation with the students in times of remote education.	3.40	HC	3.49	HC	3.31	HC
6. uses both asynchronous and synchronous in the delivery of instruction.	3.40	HC	3.22	C	3.35	HC
7. always provides response and entertain questions from the students.	3.56	HC	3.47	C	3.47	HC
Composite	3.39	HC	3.33	HC	3.31	HC

Legend: 1.00 – 1.74, Not Competent (NC); 1.75 – 2.49, Less Competent (LC); 2.50 – 3.24, Competent (C); 3.25 – 4.00, Highly Competent (HC)

As shown in the Table on teachers' competencies in the teaching of science in terms instructional delivery, it was found out that the composite weighted mean of the teachers was 3.39, principals 3.33 and master teachers 3.31 which were interpreted as Highly Competent respectively. This denotes that the science teachers had well-designed and planned teaching instruction that offers sufficient opportunities for successful acquisition of skills and knowledge. Instructional delivery is that the teacher will build on existing knowledge, differentiate instruction, and incorporate different strategies into lessons. Through modeling of the outstanding teachers, master teachers and school principals, this shows an impact to the beginning teachers on how to successfully apply their knowledge and skills in the delivery of instructions. This was supported by (Ross, 2019) that relationship between the student, the teacher, the content, and the instructor is referred to as instructional delivery. To interact with students about academic instructional delivery and

to offer teaching, teachers must use a variety of instructional tactics that encourage student involvement. During pandemic, it was evident that the science teachers utilized recorded video lesson as a supplemental on the topics that she/he had discussed to ensure the continuity of learning.

Table 11. *Teachers' Competencies in the Teaching of Science in Terms of Formative Assessment*

<i>The Science teacher ...</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Principals</i>		<i>Master Teachers</i>	
	<i>w\bar{x}</i>	<i>VD</i>	<i>w\bar{x}</i>	<i>VD</i>	<i>w\bar{x}</i>	<i>VD</i>
	1. provides feedback with the students to improve their teaching and by students to improve their learning despite the limited face-to-face situation.	3.40	HC	3.38	HC	3.27
2. do the formative assessment to check the students' weaknesses and strength.	3.51	HC	3.18	C	3.38	HC
3. do formative assessment through online or in Google platform.	2.93	C	2.91	C	3.20	C
4. uses the art of questioning as a formative assessment.	3.44	HC	3.42	HC	3.29	HC
5. uses blended processing activities and varied types of formative assessment to the students.	3.42	HC	3.44	HC	3.35	HC
6. implements and interprets various types of formal and informal assessments as determined by individual student needs.	3.42	HC	3.44	HC	3.45	HC
7. does explain the criteria in evaluating the performance of the students.	3.44	HC	3.47	HC	3.44	HC
Composite	3.36	HC	3.32	HC	3.34	HC

Legend: 1.00 – 1.74, Not Competent (NC); 1.75 – 2.49, Less Competent (LC); 2.50 – 3.24, Competent (C); 3.25 – 4.00, Highly Competent (HC)

Based on the results, it was found out the composite weighted mean on the teachers' competencies in the teaching of science in terms of formative assessment as rated by the teachers was 3.36, principals were 3.32 and master teachers was 3.34 which interpreted by Highly Competent. This denotes that the science teacher had implemented and interpreted various types of formal and informal assessments as determined by individual student needs. The science teachers conduct formative assessments to adjust lessons, instructional strategies, and academic support with the students. Through formative assessments, it would help the science teachers identify concepts that students are having trouble understanding, skills they are having trouble picking up, or learning standards they have not yet attained. This was supported by Orlando (2020) One of the main purposes of formative assessment is to provide feedback to students' performance on where they are on the spectrum of conceptual understanding.

Table 12. *Teachers' Competencies in the Teaching of Science in Terms of Personal Competencies*

<i>The Science teacher ...</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Principals</i>		<i>Master Teachers</i>	
	<i>w\bar{x}</i>	<i>VD</i>	<i>w\bar{x}</i>	<i>VD</i>	<i>w\bar{x}</i>	<i>VD</i>
	1. always motivates and encourage students to do more scientific activities despite of the limited engagement.	3.35	HC	3.15	C	3.27
2. understands the situation of the blended learning and able to organize inclusiveness among students.	3.45	HC	3.38	HC	3.31	HC
3. promotes integrity and fairness judgement among students both in online class and in limited face-to-face instruction.	3.49	HC	3.47	HC	3.38	HC
4. always understands why other students under limited face-to-face contact perform better than those in on-line class.	3.51	HC	3.49	HC	3.27	HC
5. teaches what the students are learning.	3.44	HC	3.25	HC	3.35	HC
6. must show an enthusiasm in the delivery of the lesson both on-line learning instruction and limited face-to-face delivery.	3.49	HC	3.40	HC	3.49	HC
7. manages classes in both online and face-to-face led classroom activities.	3.55	HC	3.31	HC	3.55	HC
Composite	3.47	HC	3.35	HC	3.37	HC

Legend: 1.00 – 1.74, Not Competent (NC); 1.75 – 2.49, Less Competent (LC); 2.50 – 3.24, Competent (C); 3.25 – 4.00, Highly Competent (HC)

Based on the Table, the composite weighted mean on teachers' competencies in the teaching of science in terms of personal competencies as rated by the teachers was 3.47, principals were 3.35 and master teachers was 3.37 which interpreted as Highly Competent. This denotes that the effective use of a teacher's personality is essential in conducting most classroom activities. The science teachers should have the personality and understands why other students under limited face-to-face contact perform better than those in on-line class. They must show an enthusiasm in the delivery of the lesson both on-line learning instruction and limited face-to-face delivery. And science teachers can manage classes in both online and face-to-face led classroom activities. Motivating, listening, collaboration, adaptability, empathy, caring, flexibility, and adaptability are some personal competencies of a good teacher. An engaging classroom presence, importance of real-world learning, sharing of best practices, and a lifelong love of learning are additional traits of effective teaching. These personal competencies were highly evident to the science teachers based on the teachers self-rating and the rating of their master teachers and school principals. According to Henson (2019) an effective teacher should be open-minded.

Based on the Table 13, it has shown that the teaching competencies of the science teachers based on classroom management, instructional delivery, formative assessment and personal competencies were Highly Competent which was rated by the teachers and master teacher, except for the classroom management which was rated by the principals as Competent. This implies that teachers have

a variety of responsibilities, but the function of classroom management is undoubtedly one of the most crucial roles of the teachers especially in times of the pandemic. Inefficient classroom management prevents effective teaching and learning from occurring.

Table 13. *Summary Table on the Teachers' Competencies in Teaching of Science*

Areas	Teachers		Principals		Master Teachers	
	\bar{wX}	VD	\bar{wX}	VD	\bar{wX}	VD
1. Classroom Management	3.35	HC	3.22	C	3.34	HC
2. Instructional Delivery	3.39	HC	3.33	HC	3.31	HC
3. Formative Assessment	3.36	HC	3.32	HC	3.34	HC
4. Personal Competencies	3.47	HC	3.35	HC	3.37	HC

Legend: 1.00 – 1.74, Not Competent (NC); 1.75 – 2.49, Less Competent (LC); 2.50 – 3.24, Competent (C); 3.25 – 4.00, Highly Competent (HC)

The lack of professional experience and knowledge, and academic shortcomings were found as poor skills as observed by the school principals. By developing their capacity to interact and communicate with teachers on classroom management, giving classroom management professional development, establishing behavioral expectations, and providing instructional and discipline support are what expected to the school principals to support teachers' classroom management. As supported by Pellegrino, Chudowsky, and Glaser (2021) that science teachers have the requisite abilities, they still need to develop such skills to enrich, improve, and investigate their teaching techniques, particularly when dealing with today's 21st-century learners.

Table 14. *Relationship between the Demographic Profile (Specialization) and the Teachers' Competencies in Teaching Science*

Specialization and...	χ^2	p-value	Decision	Remark
Classroom Management	0.97	0.614	Fail to reject Ho	Not significant
Instructional Delivery	1.93	0.380	Fail to reject Ho	Not significant
Formative Assessment	2.09	0.352	Fail to reject Ho	Not significant
Personal Competencies	2.98	0.225	Fail to reject Ho	Not significant

Table 14 showed that the teachers' specialization has no significant relationship to their competence in teaching Science in terms of classroom management ($p = 0.614 > \alpha = 0.05$), instructional delivery ($p = 0.380 > \alpha = 0.05$), formative assessment ($p = 0.352 > \alpha = 0.05$), and personal competencies ($p = 0.225 > \alpha = 0.05$). These findings signify that the teachers' specialization cannot account to their competence in teaching Science. This implies that there is not enough evidence to support the hypotheses. In other words, the study's findings do not provide convincing evidence that the variables being studied are related or have significant effect on each other. Nonetheless, it is important to note that non-significant results should not be equated with being insignificant or meaningless. According to Egeberg and McConney (2016) these provide valuable information that can contribute to the collective knowledge and guide for future research.

Conclusions

Science teachers as educators should demonstrate the following competencies such as effective classroom management, instructional delivery, formative assessment, and personal competencies. A range of competencies should be employed to promote purposeful learning with the students. Effective instructional delivery which is knowing when and how to use current educational instructional materials, as well as the choosing most appropriate type and level of instruction to maximize student learning. Effective formative assessment in which incorporating formal tests; responses to quizzes; evaluation of classroom assignments, student performances and projects, and standardized achievement tests to understand what students have learned. Personal competencies where science teachers are compassionate, empathetic to the students understanding and motivated to share her knowledge to the students. These identified competencies are practices of science teachers and are embedded in training which also signify capability of science teachers to carry out a specific task. These competencies could be integrated in the education practices of the teachers for these are crucial in achieving the goal of Department of Education for quality teaching and learning. Defining teachers' competencies will contribute to the implementation of the quality of the educational system which positively affects the students' learning outcomes. Thus, the researcher assessed the teachers' teaching competencies and performances in science reflective to the new normal flexible learning modalities and used the result of this study as the basis for crafting a teacher support model

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